

The Friends, Families and Travellers (FFT) LabDay - Crystal's Vardo

[Friends, Families and Travellers](#) (FFT) have a long history of leading on training, campaigns, producing educational materials, curating artistic collaborations and working horizontally with Gypsy, Roma and Travellers communities. In 2021, Suzanna King approached C-DaRE's Rosa Cisneros to choreograph the dance portion of the restaging of *Crystal's Vardo*, a piece directed by King herself. The piece was being reworked for camera and King was keen to develop certain sections and produce a teacher's resource pack. For this capacity building event, Cisneros, King, Kavanagh Rose Rattigan (actor), Stewart Barham (actor), Sarah-Jane Miller (musician) discussed *Crystal's Vardo*, the importance of such productions in reflecting on racism and bullying and the value of generating teacher's resources. Participants had the opportunity to watch excerpts of the work, meet part of the cast, have access to the teacher's materials and ask the team questions about how to implement this work in their own settings.

Key takeaways:

- The power of theatre, dance and music to change hearts and minds, educate and raise awareness of the persecution of the Gypsy, Roma and Traveller (GRT) communities through the centuries
- The importance of bringing GRT histories to the school curriculum through drama
- The power of 'leaving one's skin in the work' and the 'mahala' (the community) that travels with you
- Crystal's Vardo and the importance of such works to reflect on racism, bullying and the value of generating teacher's resources.
- Resources are available to support implementing the work in their educational environments and FFT is available to support that process.
- The Yellow Couch Convo Podcast Series is a resource and modern day oral history project that allows for contemporary Gypsy Roma Traveller voices to be heard. <https://soundcloud.com/user-566749993/sets/eriac-yellow-couch-convos>

Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xOJnuDaZpUA>

Widen European Access
to Cultural Communities
Via Europeana

Co-financed by the European Union
Connecting Europe Facility